

10th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress
A Typology of Action Research for Scholar-Practitioners

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ABSTRACT

Many authors are engaged in important projects involving pure research and applied research; however, few conduct action research that bring about positive change in real life. The objectives of this article are fivefold, which correspond with the research questions: 1) what is action research? 2) What are the different types of action research? 3) In which fields is action research employed? 4) What are the benefits of action research? 5) What are the drawbacks of action research? The literature cites the importance of reflective practices to promote change. While this article is based on deductive desktop research, the actual conduct of action research necessitates investment of resources and time for inductive field work as well as produce actual change as the product and outcomes of the research. The findings discovered that there are several types of action research, each of which serves a different function. One type of action research is not better than another; rather, each type of action serves a different purpose. Authors are invited to consider utilizing action research at least in one of their research projects soon, with the aim of taking part as a change agent in the transformation of one aspect of society: be that of business, community, education, organization, or society at large.

Keywords: Action Research, Community-Based Action Research, Methodology, Participatory Action Research, Research

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Problem

When researchers engage in addressing problematic issues as well as changing an aspect of the material world, they are engaged in action research. By means of social investigation and collaborative work, they are engaged in ameliorating social realities one way or the other. While action research had its genesis in the field of education, today, it is widely used also in community, health, business, and social science research. Action research bridges the gap between theory and practice.

Problem Statement

While action research is being used by some researchers, many do not know that different types of action research exist. They do not know how action research can be applied in their actions for change (Zuber-Skerritt, 2022). To employ action research, they need to know the strengths and weaknesses in using this research methodology.

Research Gaps

For those who are exposed to this methodology, many believe that there is only one type of action research and that it is monolithic. As there is a deficiency in the comprehensive analysis of action research, there is a dearth of understanding regarding the multiplicity of action research as well.

Purpose of this Article

The purpose of this article was to explain and explore the diverse types of action research, their uses, as well as their merits and demerits.

Research Questions

This article responded to the following queries:

1. What is action research?
2. What are the different types of action research?
3. In which fields are they utilized?
4. What are their strengths?
5. What are their weaknesses?

Specific Objectives of the Article

Based on the foregoing research questions, the objectives this paper were the following:

1. To explain what action research is
2. To identify the different types of action research
3. To determine in which areas they are employed
4. To discuss their strengths
5. To discuss their weaknesses

Significance of This Article

This article supports researchers to understand what action research is, in which areas they are employed, and to identify where they can apply the research methodology of action research in their investigative projects for change. These researchers are in such fields as business, educational settings, organizational development, and organizational change. It contributes to knowing the best fit model for utilization in their research.

Rationale of the Article

Understanding the different types of action research is crucial for success in bringing about positive transformation in business, classroom, community, and organization.

Coverage of the Article

The scope of this article is an overview of the different types of action research, a critical analysis, and the fields where they are applied. This paper provided a description, a typology of the different methodologies, case examples, strengths and weaknesses, as well as recommendations at the end. It is limited to qualitative analysis. For its delimitation, the paper stressed clarity of the concepts as well as applications in the real world. It neither performed an empirical test nor a data-driven investigation. Furthermore, it is focused on action research as a methodology and a process, rather than examining in great depth case analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review provided the key term that gave direction to this article. It compared and contrasted action research with other mainstream types of research. They include collaboration, the genesis and evolution of this methodology, some variants, and reflective practice. This section ended with the gap that this article filled.

There are three major types of research: pure research, applied research, and action research. Firstly, pure research utilizes theory and searches for knowledge for the sake of knowledge. Examples of pure research include biology, chemistry, humanities, physics, sociology, and social sciences. Secondly, applied research aims for the technical application of skills based on the knowledge from pure research. Examples of applied research include aerospace, dentistry, engineering, medicine, nursing, and social work. Thirdly, action research, far from searching for knowledge for the sake of knowledge only, seeks to improve social context or practice, at school, in businesses, communities, or organizations. Action research can benefit the classroom, businesses, community, or the country. See Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Major Types of Research
Source: ©2024 Rey Ty

Action research is an iterative endeavor which requires the principal investigator to engage in collaboration with the people, school, organization or community under research. Action research was initiated formally as such in 1946 in the field of education (Lewin, 1946). For this reason, many action research articles are related to schools, education, teachers, administrators, and students (Mills, 2018). Later, however, action research has evolved into different fields. It started to be applied in community research to promote positive change, to the use of feminist perspectives, as well as to the application in organizational development and change. From its beginnings in education, action research is now used in business, community development, management, marketing, organizational development, organizational change, planning, political mobilization, public administration, social movements, social work, and other applied fields and disciplines.

Communities, organizations, and schools must engage in reflective practice to understand the current situation and how to meet the changing needs. Failing to do so could lead to being obsolete and not meeting the expectations of their stakeholders. Examples include Kodak, mainstream media, My Space, Nokia,

10th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress
physical shopping malls, and Yahoo (The Global Hues, 2024). Had they engaged in action research, their companies would have been more competitive, instead of lagging behind.

Some of the different variants of action research include the following: arts-based action research, basic action research, classroom action research, collaborative action research, critical participatory action research, digital community participatory action research, educational action research, community-based participatory action research, organizational action research, participatory action research, school action research, and youth community participatory action research.

This paper filled the knowledge gap of many researchers by presenting systematically a comparative analysis of this methodology by way of a typology with a view to guide researchers for their proper utilization.

METHODOLOGY

Philosophy

In traditional research, the principal investigator is an objective observer from the outside who uses etic perspectives. However, in action research, the principal investigator is engaged in the process of working for positive change together with all the stakeholders and is therefore an insider using an emic viewpoint. The conduct of action research by nature is materialist, as it delves into the existing situation or condition upon which positive changes are sought and will be brought to bear.

Research Design

This paper is a qualitative exploration of the different variants of action research. Action research itself could employ qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods.

Research Approach

This paper itself is based upon existing literature and is therefore deductive. However, action research as such, which this article discussed is inductive, investigating real-world issues towards which actions for transformations are directed.

Research Strategy

Action research by itself is a form of research strategy in which the research engages with stakeholders with a view for transformation.

Data Collection Methods

Data collected for this article were based on existing literature on matters related to action research as a methodology as well as examples of the utilization of action research. For the actual action research, data are gathered through field work and involvement in the stakeholders' planning for changes.

Sources of Research Data

The sources employed here were from academic journals, books, and online sources. Diverse materials were utilized, which presented distinct viewpoints. They ranged from the seminal or classical work (Lewin, 1946) to cutting-edge materials on action research.

Comparative Data Analysis Methods

Relevant materials were gathered for the preparation of this article, after which the materials were subjected to comparative descriptive analysis through the emergent thematic coding. By doing so, a summary of the description of the data was provided. Different models of action research emerged in the process of coding.

Data Interpretation Methods

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Upon review and reflection of the data that emerged from the reading materials, the codes and themes were organized into a typology of the different types of action research, based on the emerging trends and patterns, as the output of this paper. This typology was the product of the grounded theory process of developing a classification of the different types of action research.

Time Horizon

Action research tends to be cross-sectional, as the focus of the research is the current situation for which changes are sought, planned, and performed.

Reflexivity

In action research, the principal researchers are not outsiders but are co-producers of knowledge in terms of their positionality. In this way, they are involved in changing the way the stakeholders are. The researcher will conduct member checking to ensure that the data are correct and that the interpretation is close to the meaning and intent of the stakeholders.

Research Ethics

Given that this article is merely desktop research, no human subjects were harmed.

FINDINGS

This article responded to five research objectives. These objectives relate to the meaning of action research, the different types of action research, the application of action research, strengths, and weaknesses.

Data Analysis

Research Objective 1

To Describe Action Research

Action research deals with the resolution of problems that exist in the material world. It involves a process that encompasses observation, planning, action, and reflection. Action research comprises participation and is iterative in procedure. It is both a systematic as well as an adaptive practical process of investigation, such as in the educational setting (Efron & Ravid, 2020) that necessitates participation which leads to solving real-world problems that makes a difference (Stringer & Ortiz Aragón, 2021). People who will be affected by changes, have their voices heard. This type of research involves the resolution of real-world challenges and simultaneously engage in the contribution of the knowledge base (Lewin, 1946).

Research Objective 2

To Identify the Different Key Types of Action Research

There are several types of action research. Here we will discuss traditional action research, participatory action research, collaborative action research, educational action research, community-based action research, feminist action research, critical action research, and organizational action research.

Traditional action research is based on the problem that the principal researcher identified. Its planning and implementation are top-down. This is the minimum level of action research. It relies solely on the knowledge and skills of the project leader. Traditional action research is applied in the resolution of issues involving the classroom as well as concerns of small organizations. In traditional action research, one key researcher with absolute power and control performs the action research.

Unlike traditional action research which is vertically top-down in its execution, participatory action research (PAR) on its part is horizontal, as it involved peer to peer participation and networking. Together the

10th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

researcher and the stakeholders are directly involved in the identification of the problem as well as the identification of potential solutions. An example is actions that involve community members in organizing their tree planting projects. Here, participation of stakeholders in research is key (Brydon-Miller, 1997). Participatory action research is more democratic than traditional action research, as stakeholders are involved in the process of change and are consulted.

Collaborative action research is based upon teams of the same level professionals who work together to deal with common concerns. An illustration involves chemical engineers working together to produce nanoparticles of titanium dioxide and zinc oxide to produce high-quality natural sunscreen. For this type of research to succeed, stakeholders must be able to work harmoniously as a team (Denzin & Giardina, 2021).

Teaching staff engage in educational action research with a view to achieve improvements in the outcomes of instruction (Efron & Ravid, 2020; Glanz, 2025). For instance, teachers conduct action research to develop a curriculum that emphasizes inclusivity (Sagor, 2016). The primary objective here is to improve the practice of teaching (Glanz, 2025). Instructors engage in research with respect to their classes. This type of research improves the academic institution and empowers instructors (Mertler, 2020).

In community-based action research, the lead investigator works with the community to search for solutions customized to their needs in solving their local problems. An instance is the digging of a well in the village so that the villagers will always have access to water (Beltran-Figueroa et al., 2011; Stringer & Ortiz Aragón, 2021). Community members are empowered to deal with matters directly affecting their communities. The production of contextualized knowledge and change comes from the ground, rather than the use of foreign abstract generalized models. A specific type of community-based participatory action research involves the youth so that they themselves decide the courses of action that need to be undertaken that benefit them directly (Brion-Meisels & Albright, 2025).

As for feminist action research, disparity in gender which is the central focus is addressed, the purpose being to bring to fore the empowerment of the marginalized gender. An example is action research on the hiring and firing policy of a multinational corporation for top-level executives to find out whether gender matters in recruitments of top minds or the inclusion of gender voices in the curriculum in educational settings (Tisdell, 1995). Here, gendered views are crucial in implementing action research. Sex workers and trafficked persons, on their part, have their own unique challenges for which there exists a participatory action research is utilized for the purpose of developing and recommending policies for their protection (Mertler, 2020).

With respect to critical action research, social investigation delves into disparities in the systemic level, calling for the advancement of social justice. An example is investigative work exposes religious, ethnic, colored, or cultural discrimination so that injustices will be addressed (Bierema, 2010; Dege, 2023; Fine & Torre, 2021; Kemmis et al., 2014). Power is unpacked and the marginalized and outcasts are empowered as the outcome of action research.

Organizational action research, in turn, deals with the improvement of elements related to organizations, such as procedures and systems. The purpose is to increase the learning of members of the organization to bring about positive organizational development and change. An illustration is the increase in the participation of team members in an organizational set up through practice of reflection (Coghlan & Brannick, 2009). See Figure 2 below for power dynamics in action research.

Figure 2: Power Dynamics in the Different Types of Action Research (AR)

Source: ©2024 Rey Ty

Research Objective 3

To Explain in Which Areas Action Research is Used

Action research is useful in many fields. Researchers use it in business, city planning, economy development, education, health, marketing, nursing, product development, social work, urban planning, and other related fields (Stringer & Ortiz Aragón, 2021). Here, some examples are discussed.

In business, human resource development, management, organizational development, and organizational change, action research is used to improve individual and organizational learning, development, and change (Bierema, 2010; Coghlan & Brannick, 2009; Gilley et al., 2008; Holton & Swanson, 2011; Merriam et al., 2007; Swanson & Holton, 1997). Change is difficult in organizational setting as people are used to traditions, rules of thumb, and normalized practices; this is the reason for which organizational action research helps in the smooth transition of organizations to move from the old organizational system to change to the new one (Andersen et al., 2024)

In education, the teaching staff improves practices in the classes (Stringer & Ortiz Aragón, 2021). This includes pedagogy, classroom, management of the classroom, time management, tweaking of testing instruments, and the like. Action research is also employed for the improvement of educational institutions (Glanz, 2025). This type of action research is also used to learn inequity among students based on their social class, caste, social status, or economic income. The purpose is to promote equity among the pupils as well as advance academic excellence across any social and economic differences among them (Sagor, 2016).

In community development, instead of relying on central, federal, or national government authorities or foreign funding agencies for improving the lives of communities, local needs are prioritized, using local wisdom. Action research for communities include such matters as water management, soil management, seed bank, sanitation, hygiene, healthcare, education, micro-loans, environmental protection, irrigation, and the like (Beltran-Figueroa et al., 2011; Gullion & Tilton, 2020; Renzo Rosales et al., 2024; Ty, 2009). Many local environmental actions, sustainable development projects, and food security measures are products of community-based participatory action research (Ty, 2016, 2021b, 2021a). An important issue today involves migrant workers and forced migration: for this concern, there is a unique action research that revolves around the needs of migrant labor (Hays, 2024).

Research Objective 4

To Discuss the Strengths of Action Research

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There are several reasons for which action research is important. First, using action research rather than traditional research is useful and powerful in situations where change is sought to solve problems in the classroom, organization, community, or society at large. Action research is not merely research for the sake of gaining knowledge, though such endeavor as such is praiseworthy. Action research is intended primarily to solve problems with which stakeholders are confronted. Second, action research is not abstract; rather, it deals with problems and solving them as the research moves along.

Third, action research responds to the actual needs of stakeholders because of the problems with which they are faced. As challenges are contextual, solutions should likewise be contextual. Here comes in action research which is an on-the-ground process of dealing with problems.

Fourth, action research is flexible. It starts with identifying the problem at hand. Next, the researchers choose one of several ways of dealing with the problem. The lead researchers could decide to act as an expert and conduct top-down traditional action research. They could decide to be more democratic and engage in horizontal participatory action research with the stakeholders. In addition, they could choose to conduct bottom-up community-based action research that empowers the grassroots community members, especially those who are marginalized or are outcasts.

Fifth, in action research, the lead investigator cannot merely sit at a library and conduct research using materials available online as e-materials or offline as hardcopy documents. Rather, the principal investigator must interact one way or the other with the stakeholders who stand to benefit from the actions arising from the research. Hence, the voices of the people under scrutiny not only surfaced but in fact play a critical role in the conduct of the research to ensure that the ensuing actions will match the expectations of the stakeholders and meet their needs. The engagement of participants in different forms is crucial in the conduct of action research. Sixth, action research relies on collaboration one way or the other: top-down, horizontal, or bottom-up.

Seventh, reflexivity is ensured in action research. Instead of being mere objective bystanders, the principal investigators are involved in both research and in change. In this way, the key researchers are engaged and have a stake in the development of positive transformation due to the research. The researcher is a co-producer of knowledge along with the people who stand to gain from the findings of the research.

Research Objective 4

To Discuss the Weaknesses of Action Research

While there are many benefits of action research, there are also some drawbacks as well. First, whereas both pure research and applied research have the power of generalizability of their findings, that is not the case with action research. As action research is based on the study of historically and socially based contexts, the findings of action research are unique to the issues specific to a given context.

Second, action research does not come by easy. Key investigators must spend a lot of resources in the conduct of the research. They need to spend time with the stakeholders prior to the conduct of the research to find out what their concerns are. Next, they must talk with the people to learn what their dreams, visions, and needs are so that they can map out a plan for positive change, after which they need to be with the stakeholders from the start of the conduct of the research until their actions bear fruit in the form of positive change. To perform all the above, finances must be allotted for food, drinks, transportation, and accommodation for the whole duration of the research.

10th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

Third, whereas the merit of action research is that the lead investigator is a co-producer of knowledge along with the stakeholders, such co-production of knowledge is also its demerit. Researchers are noteworthy for engaging in positive change for and with the stakeholders. However, in doing so, the researchers could potentially ignore missteps, errors, omissions, and problems in the conduct of research as they are too closely linked and attached with the expected outcome for positive change.

CONCLUSION

Summary

Action research arose from the need to deal with the need to solve problems and bring about positive change. There are several types of action research, some of which are traditional, participatory, collaborative, educational, community-based, feminist, critical, and organizational. Each type of action research has its own unique uses, merits, and demerits. The summary of this paper is presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: A Typology of Action Research for Scholar-Practitioners
Source: ©2024 Rey Ty

Now What? Recommendations

First, for the successful employment of action research, the principal investigators must first know and understand the context which needs actions for social change. Second, as there are many types of action research, principal investigators must understand and use the best-fit model. Third, collaboration is key for the meaningful and successful implementation of action research. Fourth, the key authors must recognize and acknowledge the role they play in the co-production of knowledge with the stakeholders. Fifth and lastly, there are potential areas of conflict as the researchers is deeply embedded with the stakeholders in business, classroom, community, organization, or society at large. Hence, engaging in action research is rife with potential conflict. Hence, key researchers must observe ethical practice when they work involves dealing with human subjects, such as in action research in general and counseling or providing psychotherapy to them (McLeod & McLeod, 2025).

Conclusion

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Researchers could develop training of trainers in action research with materials as well as enroll in these courses. All researchers are encouraged to use action research. It can be used in business planning, community health, education, policy development, project planning, and elsewhere. Schools, communities, and organizations will stand to benefit from the fruits of action research. Everyone is transformed when engaged in action research, which promotes intellectual and social growth, as learning, action, and reflection are all integral in action research. Will you use action research in your next research project?

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10th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

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